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Effects of Cooperative Learning Method on Senior Secondary Students' Achievement in Financial Accounting in Secondary Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of cooperative learning method on senior secondary students' achievement in financial accounting. Six research questions and six null hypotheses guided the study. The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental research design using pre-test, post-test non equivalent control group. The population of the study comprised all senior secondary two (SS II) students in seventy six (76) government secondary schools in Abakaliki Education Zone totaling nine hundred and six (906) students. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select one hundred and twenty (120) students from the four sampled schools. Two schools were assigned two experimental groups while the other two schools were assigned to control group. The researcher developed two instructional packages for the experiment. Experimental group was guided using cooperative learning method while the control group was guided using individualized learning method. The instrument for data collection is financial accounting achievement Test (FAAT). The instrument is validated by three experts, two from Business Education Department and one from Science Education Department all from Ebonyi State University Abakaliki. FAAT were trial tested on SS II students of Onueke Education Zone. The reliability of FAAT was tested for internal consistency using Kuder-Richardson formula (K-R-20) and reliability of 0.97 was obtained. Data generated from FAAT is analyzed using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at alpha level of 0.05. The result of the study revealed that cooperative learning strategy is more effective than the conventional (individualized learning) approach in facilitating students' achievement in accounting. Male students performed better than their female counterparts when they learn accounting using the cooperative learning approach. The educational implication of the findings is that cooperative learning methods should be adopted by financial accounting teacher in their instructional delivery, so that students could work cooperatively. Based on the findings, the study recommended that cooperative learning method should be utilized in instructional strategies for financial accounting because this method caters for students' differences in groups to improve their achievement and interest in financial accounting.

Keywords: Cooperative learning method, Secondary Students, Achievement, Financial Accounting

INTRODUCTION

The essence of any educational programme is to ensure that the products are equipped with relevant knowledge, skills and attitude needed to contribute meaningfully to the economic development of the nation (Ediagbonya in Ezeoruonye 2021). Olawoyin, Adeleye and Olaniyi (2015), had stated that for a nation to progress and witness development, she must give the right education that is capable of

developing the youths into sound and responsible citizens as well as fully integrating them into the community. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2023), stated that one of the aims and objectives of education is to help the child acquire appropriate productive skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment to live in and contribute to societal development. In order to achieve the goals and objectives of education in Nigeria, government has geared efforts towards making individuals contribute to the growth of the nation's economy and become self-reliant through well-developed curriculum covering academic and vocational subjects at the secondary school level. At the junior secondary level, business studies is taught as a pre-vocational subject with Book-keeping as an integral part. At the senior secondary school level, the curriculum covers vocational and commercial subjects such as Financial Accounting (Eremie, 2018).

Financial Accounting is one of the vocational subjects taught in senior secondary schools. Financial Accounting is the systematic act of recording, classifying, selecting, analyzing and interpreting financial data which enables the users to make decisions (Chukwu in Agbede & Ba'aba 2019). The aim is to provide appropriate knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies necessary for students to study higher and/ live in, and contribute meaningfully to the development of the nation and dynamic business environment. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2024) stated that the broad goal of secondary school education (also referred to as post basic education) is to prepare individuals for useful living within the society and higher education. To achieve this objective, at the Junior Secondary School, Bookkeeping (Prevocational subject) is taught as a component of Business Studies to prepare the students towards the choice of any of the business components including Financial Accounting at the senior secondary level.

Secondary school, according to Ikegbusi (2016), is the intermediate between elementary school and tertiary institution and usually offering general, technical, vocational or tertiary school preparatory courses. It runs for six years in Nigeria. The period is divided into three years junior secondary school and three years senior secondary school. Senior secondary school is the upper and last part of secondary school at the end of which a student writes external examinations known as Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) organized by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and/or National Examination Council (NECO). Secondary education is the education that is concerned with the provision of competencies required for useful living to those whose education is terminated at the secondary school level (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2024). The general objectives of financial accounting in senior secondary education as stated in the National curriculum for senior secondary schools (NERDC, 2019) are: to provide specialized instruction that will prepare students for careers in book-keeping and accounting fields; to provide fundamental instruction that will help students to assume their economic role as consumer, workers and citizen; to provide background instruction that will assist students in preparing for other professional careers requiring advanced study in book-keeping and accounting skills for personal use in the future with particular emphasis on wise planning of income and expenditure. The objectives are geared towards making the students to value the principle and importance of financial accounting, lay a solid and sound foundation for further studies in accounting at the tertiary level, and also assess students' knowledge of basic accounting concepts, conventions and principles and their application to modern business activities.

The need for improvement is evidenced in the students' performance shown in National Examination Council (NECO) and West Africa Senior Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in Ebonyi State for years 2020-2022. The performance of secondary school students in financial accounting in Ebonyi State equally reflects the performance of secondary schools in Abakaliki Education Zone of Ebonyi State. The poor performance is also evidenced in the unified examination in secondary schools in Ebonyi State covering 2019/2020 session, which revealed that 61% performance rate below credit level and 39% at credit level in 84 public secondary schools in Abakaliki Education Zone of Ebonyi State (Ebonyi State Ministry of Education, 2023).

According to the WAEC and NECO report in Ebonyi State ministry on students' performance in financial accounting in Ebonyi State since 2017 to 2022 indicated that most students performed poorly in the subject. Sunday and Kola in Nweze (2022) indicated that the alarming rate of poor academic achievement

in financial accounting has generated growing concern and has been an issue of utmost concern to parents, researchers, educators and administrators in Nigeria (Uwezo, 2020, Ndika, Mary ann & Ubani, 2017). Irrespective of the unrelenting efforts of Ebonyi State Government to boost the performance of secondary school students in the State, the case of low academic achievement of secondary school students in quantitative subjects such as financial accounting still persist (Onyali, Akinforlarin & Famuti 2018), hence the need for improvement in students academic achievement in financial accounting. The academic achievement of the students could be defined as individual progress, improvement in terms of acquired knowledge, skills and competences.

Academic Achievement of the students is one of the key factors that show that there is change in the behaviour of the students which implies that learning has taken place. Academic achievement of the students has been an issue of utmost concern to researchers, educators and administrators in Nigeria (Ndika, Maryann & Ubani, 2017). Academic Achievement of the students is one of the key factors that show that there is change in the behaviour of the students which implies that learning has taken place. Academic achievement of a learner is the ability of the learner to study, retain knowledge and recollect facts and being able to communicate his/her knowledge orally or in written form even under examination conditions. It is characterized by the motives, goals and values of the students (Ngwoke, 2024). Academic achievement of the students comprises their performance in quiz, test, continuous assessment and examination among others. Students' academic achievement can either be positive or negative. Asif and Mumtaz (2017) discovered that the results on post-test showed that corporative learning method has significant effect on the achievement of students in learning Social Studies. Igbal (2014) found that there was a significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught by corporative learning and those taught using individualized method. Gadzama (2017) investigated the effect of corporative learning method of teaching on the achievement of students in financial accounting in Obanliku Local Government Area of Cross River State and revealed that cooperative learning methods promotes higher achievement of students in financial accounting than individualized methods of learning. Academic achievement of students can be affected by so many factors which include student's interest in learning, student's background, home environment, gender, teachers' qualification, teaching method, to mention just a few. Students achievement in financial accounting has been observed from literature to be hindered by many factors such as teachers' insensitivity to the nature of financial accounting when planning instructional activities in the classroom (Olarinoye, 2015). In spite of the advocacy that financial accounting teachers should complement traditional method of teaching with innovative methods (McManus & Gettinger 2019). Teachers are, therefore, required to complement innovative strategies to improve the academic achievement of students.

Learning method according to Weinstein and Mayer in Danjuma (2015) is "behavior and thoughts that a learner engages in during learning" which are "Intended to influence the learner's encoding process". Learning strategies are involved on all learning, regardless of the content and context. Learning methods are thus used in learning Financial Accounting, business studies, science, English language and other subjects both in classroom settings and more informal learning environment. Undoubtedly, the application of cooperative learning methods has the potency of enhancing effective learning in financial accounting in senior secondary school. This learning strategy actively involves learners at all levels of instructional delivery by making them active recipients, contributors and participants of instructional contents and evaluation. Learning methods will help students to gain and create both academic and social relationships as well as to accomplish shared goals. Through such kind of interactions, students learn to cross-examine issues, share ideas, elucidate differences, and construct new understandings.

In Ebonyi State, the researcher in her experiences as a teacher observed that several methods of learning have been employed in teaching accounting for some years taken in West Africa Senior Secondary School Certificate which include: lecture, demonstration, discussion, dramatization, enquiry, field experiment, problem solving, etc. Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2023) stated most teachers adopt traditional method of teaching financial accounting which is oral presentation of ideas, concepts and principles to the students. In this method of teaching, the student does not contribute to the teaching and learning process,

all they do is to listen to the teacher and put down their notes while the teacher dominate the class. Jimoh (2024) explained that conventional method of teaching is an instructional strategy which affords the teacher the opportunity to present a wide content to a large class of students with little or no interaction among students and even the teacher. Adunfe (2015) opined that demonstration method is a teaching strategy where a pre-packaged instructional content is delivered by the teacher to a large audience with minimal students-teacher interaction. Despite all the methods mentioned above the quest for better method of teaching in which learning can have better effect on the learners change in behavior has been a continuous struggle, hence the need to incorporate modern instructional strategies like cooperative learning method of financial accounting.

Cooperative learning method is an instructional method in which students work in small group to accomplish a common learning goal under the guidance of the teacher. Johnson and Holubec in Gazama and Azih (2019) defined cooperative method of learning as the instructional use of small group in which the students work together to maximize their own and each other's learning. In cooperative method of learning, the students are assigned to small groups by the teacher for the purpose of achieving group goal; students of same group as well as personal gain in their academic work. The students of cooperative group do not assume mastery of the effort which leads to the success of the group as each member actively contributes to the success of the group. Cooperative learning methods offer students the possibility to learn by applying knowledge in an environment more similar to the one they will encounter in their future work in life.

Gender is one factor confronting teaching and learning in schools. In Nigeria boys are encouraged to study science courses like engineering, architecture, building technology and word work, auto-mechanic, electrical/electronics, medicine while female are encouraged to go into other arts and management courses like accountancy, banking and finance and education. Gender has to do with the differences in sex (male or female). Okon in Gazama and Azih (2019) defined gender as the fact of being male or female, efficiently when considered with reference to social and cultural difference. Gender referred to the varied socially and culturally constructed roles, qualities, behavior and so on that are ascribed to men and women by different societies. Neboh in Eya (2022) stated that opinion and findings about gender have been diverse. Studies by researchers have shown that gender influences student's interest and achievement. Some people assumed that female students are afraid of subjects involving calculation. Financial Accounting being a subject that involves calculation of figures may be assumed to be one of the subjects that females are afraid of studying. However, today many female students have gone into the field of accounting competing with their male counterparts in the accounting profession as can be seen; holding positions in various sectors that involve the use of Accounting skills and competencies. A study conducted by Fabunmi (2018) revealed that gender composition has a significant relationship with students' academic achievement and that gender composition has a significant influence on secondary school student's academic achievement. Diovu in Eya (2022) revealed that the interaction effects of treatment by gender on students' overall cognitive achievement in chemistry were not significant. This findings was contrary to the findings of Ureme (2023) who revealed that there was a difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics using project method in favour of females. This shows that there is an inconsistent finding about gender differences and academic achievement. Due to this divergent findings from different studies on students' academic achievement and interest, the present study concentrate on finding the effects of cooperative learning method on senior secondary students' interest and achievement in financial accounting.

Statement of the Problem

Trends in students' achievement and interest in Financial Accounting as a career subject at the senior secondary school level have been quite discouraging. Students conceive financial accounting erroneously to be a very difficult subject in concepts and application. As a result the number of students offering the subject has continued to dwindle and the academic achievements of those that offer it have been persistently low. The low performance of students could be attributed to the way Financial Accounting is handled by the teachers which has a significant effect on students' comprehension, critical thinking,

assimilation and interest. Researchers such as Yalams and Fatokin in Eya (2022) and Nweze (2022) have identified some factors to be contributory to students' poor academic achievements and interest in Financial Accounting.

These factors include students' study habits, lack of facilities, inappropriate teaching and learning strategy used by the teachers in schools do not encourage students' active participation in the instructional process and students' loss of interests in the prevalent use of conventional learning methods. The resultant effect of this has always being poor academic achievements of students. This may be same in the learning of Financial Accounting in secondary schools in Abakaliki Education zone of Ebonyi State as students' academic achievement in WAEC and NECO examinations showed that students from Abakaliki Education Zone performed poorly in Financial Accounting and students still show low interest in the subject and few candidates entering Financial Accounting as one among the subjects to write in the external examinations.

In view of the above, there is the need to conduct a study on an innovative and participatory teaching and learning method where students could become active participants in the learning process. One of such methods is cooperative learning instructional models. Though, cooperative learning strategy as teaching methods may be known by Financial Accounting teachers and students in secondary schools, but its effect on the academic achievements and interest of students may not be clearly known in Abakaliki Education Zone. This study therefore seeks to investigate the effects of cooperative learning method on senior secondary student's interest and achievement in financial accounting.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effects of cooperative learning method on senior secondary students' achievement in financial accounting. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Mean achievement score of students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods and those that learnt using individualized method.
2. Mean achievement score of male and female students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods.
3. Interaction effects of methods and gender on students' achievement score in Financial Accounting.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods and those that learnt using individualized learning methods?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods?
3. What are the interaction effects of methods and gender on students' achievement score in Financial Accounting?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods and those that learnt using individualized learning methods.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning methods.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant interaction effect of methods and gender on students' achievement score in Financial Accounting.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental research design using pre-test, post-test non equivalent control group. The population of the study comprised all senior secondary two (SS II) students in seventy six (76) government secondary schools in Abakaliki Education Zone totaling nine hundred and six (906) students. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select one hundred and

twenty (120) students from the four sampled schools. Two schools were assigned two experimental groups while the other two schools were assigned to control group. The researcher developed two instructional packages for the experiment. Experimental group was guided using cooperative learning method while the control group was guided using individualized learning method. Financial accounting achievement Test (FAAT) and financial Accounting Interest Inventory (FAII) were used to generate data on students' achievement and interest in financial accounting. These instruments were validated by three experts, two from Business Education Department and one from Science Education Department all from Ebonyi State University Abakaliki. FAAT and FAII were trial tested on SS II students of Onueke Education Zone. The reliability of FAAT was tested for internal consistency using Kuder-Richardson formula (K-R-20) and reliability of 0.97 was obtained. FAII was divided into four clusters and were also tested for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha method. The individual clusters yielded the following coefficients: 0.62, 0.64; 0.74; and 0.66. Data generated from FAAT and FAII were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at alpha level of 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the mean achievement scores of students who learnt financial accounting using cooperative learning method and those that learnt using individualized learning method?*

Data collected with the Accounting Achievement Test was used to answer this research question. Pretest and posttest data for both the treatment and control groups were analyzed simultaneously using adjusted mean approach. Summary of result is shown on Table1

Table1: effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Students Mean Achievement in Accounting

Groups	N	Adjusted Mean	Standard dev.
Cooperative Learning approach	56	67.16	12.14
Individualized (Conventional) Approach	58	54.52	8.61

Result of data analysis summarized on Table1 shows that the cooperative learning strategy is more effective than the conventional (individualized learning) approach in facilitating students achievement in accounting.

Research Question 2: *What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt accounting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy?*

Data collected with the Accounting Achievement Test for male and female students for the treatment group only was used to answer this research question. Pretest and posttest data were also analyzed simultaneously using adjusted mean approach. Summary of result is shown on Table2

Table 2: Mean Score of male and female students who learnt accounting using the Cooperative Learning approach

Location	N	Adjusted Mean	Standard deviation
Male	25	69.16	13.60
Female	31	65.55	10.76

Summary of result on Table2 indicates that male students performed better than their female counterparts when they learn accounting using the cooperative learning approach.

Research Question 3: *What is the interaction effect of methods and gender on students mean achievement in accounting?*

Data on achievement for male and female students who learnt Accounting using cooperative learning strategy and those that learnt with the conventional individualized approach were used to answer this research question. Summary of result is presented on Table3

Table3: Interaction effect of Method and Gender on Students Means Achievement Scores in Accounting

Method	Gender	
	Male	Female
Cooperative learning strategy (Treatment)	69.16	65.55
Conventional Method (control)	53.73	56.16

As shown in Table3 the cooperative learning strategy is superior to the conventional method at the two levels of gender. For both male and female students the mean achievement scores are higher for the cooperative learning strategy. This implies that there is no interaction between method and gender on students mean achievement in Accounting.

Hypotheses

HO₁: *There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students who learnt accounting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy and those that learnt using the conventional (individualized) approach*

HO₃: *The interaction effects of methods and gender on students mean achievement in accounting will not be statistically significant*

Data collected with the Accounting Achievement Test for both the treatment and the control groups were used to test hypotheses 1 and 3. Pretest and posttest data for both the treatment and control groups were analyzed simultaneously using Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) with the pretest serving as the covariate and the posttest as the dependent variable. Summary of result is shown on Table7

Table7: Analysis of Co-Variance for students overall Accounting Achievement Scores By Learning Strategies and Interactions.

Source of variation	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F	f-probability
Covariates (Pretest)	7321.207	1	7321.207	145.190	.000
Main Effects	3941.908	2	1970.954	39.087	.000
Method	3905.018	1	3905.018	77.442	.000
Gender	37.972	1	37.972	.753	.387
2-way Interactions: (Method and Gender)	121.136	1	121.136	2.402	.124
Explained	11384.251	4	2846.063	56.442	.000
Residual	5496.319	109	50.425		
Total	16880.570	113	149.386		

For hypothesis 1, the ANCOVA table shows that the level of significance (0.05) is greater than the F-probability value (.000). The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis when the level of significance exceeds the given probability level. Since the level of significance (0.05) is greater than the f-probability value (.000), the null hypothesis was rejected. The researcher, therefore, concludes that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students who learnt Accounting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy and those that learnt using the conventional approach.

For hypothesis 3, summary of data analysis on Table7 reveals that for two way interactions between methods and gender, the f-probability value at 0.05 significance level is .0124. Because the alpha level (0.05) is less than the F. probability value (.124), the researcher upholds the null hypothesis and also infers that there is no significant interaction between instructional methods and gender on students' mean achievement in accounting.

HO₂: *There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt accounting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy*

Pretest and posttest data from the treatment group only were used to test these two hypotheses using ANCOVA. Summary of data analysis is presented on Table8

Table8: Analysis of Co-Variance of Mean Achievement Scores of students by Gender who Learnt Accounting using Cooperative Learning Strategy (Treatment group only).

Source of variation	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F	F- probability
Covariates (Pretest)	5138.827	1	5138.827	96.727	.000
Main Effects (Gender)	145.003	1	145.003	2.729	.104
Explained	5283.830	2	2641.915	49.728	.000
Residual	2815.724	53	53.127		
Total	8099.554	55	147.265		

Summary of data analysis shows that for hypothesis 2 the alpha level (0.05) is less than the F-probability value (.104). In line with the decision rule the researcher upheld the null hypothesis and concludes that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt accounting using the Cooperative Learning method

DISCUSSION

The result of the analysis in Table 1 showed that the cooperative learning strategy is more effective than the conventional (individualized learning) approach in facilitating students achievement in accounting. Also the test of hypothesis as contained in Table 7 revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students who learnt Accounting using the Cooperative Learning Strategy and those that learnt using the conventional approach. Result of the findings in this present study is in relationship with Jalinus and Nabawa, there is persuasive evidence that cooperative methods achieve at higher levels of thought and retain information longer than students who work quietly as individuals. Furthermore, the development of interpersonal skills is as important as the learning itself in cooperative learning. The development of social skills in group work-learning to cooperate is key to high quality group work. Furthermore, in agreement to this finding of the study, Lazarus (2014) found a significant difference in Mathematics achievement of participant exposed to peer tutoring, cooperative learning, and the control group. Further analysis revealed that students exposed to cooperative learning instructional strategy performs better than students exposed peer tutoring and the control.

These findings are line with the study of Tran (2014) who held that students who engaged in learning together (corporative learning) produced a higher overall improvement scores in post-test than those taught using individualized learning methods. The finding is also in agreement with Asif and Mumtaz (2017) who discovered that the results on post-test showed that corporative learning method has significant effect on the achievement of students in learning Social Studies. Igbal (2014) also agreed with this finding that there was a significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught by corporative learning and those taught using individualized method. Gadzama (2017) investigated the effect of corporative learning method of teaching on the achievement and interest of students in financial accounting in Obanliku Local Government Area of Cross River State and revealed that cooperative learning methods promotes higher achievement and interest of students in financial accounting than individualized methods of learning. The above studies are in agreement and support that cooperative learning method is more effective in learning and a more preferred methods.

In Table 2, the result showed that male students performed better than their female counterparts when they learn accounting using the cooperative learning approach. Furthermore, analysis in Table 8 shows that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students that learnt financial accounting using the cooperative learning method. The finding is in agreement with Asif and Mumtaz (2017) who stated cooperative learning approach positively affected the achievement of both male and female students. Adie (2018) also corroborated the finding of the study when he stated that there was no pronounced effect on the mean achievement of male and female students in financial accounting. The findings of this study are in consonance with Assimonye (2013) who found that hypothetical testing

revealed that sex did not significantly enhance achievement in the use of cooperative learning strategy in Mathematics. This is also in line with the findings of Iwuwa et al (2017) who observed that equality in the achievement of male and female students who were exposed to cooperative learning approach.

This findings is at variance with Ewah (2016) who found that male students had lower scores on all of the standardized tests, being uniformly rated as not performing well in the area of reading, written expression, mathematics and spelling. The study in Table 2 equally noted that the higher rate of educational under-achievement of male students was adequately explained by gender related differences in classroom behavior. Result from the present study in Table 3 further opposed the findings of Roberts in Agim (2016) which revealed that female students have general tendency to think in negative ways about the task in which they are engaged. This attitude of female students may affect their academic performance as this requires interaction with others through discussion in groups.

However, findings in this present study is in conformity with that of Umar, Yagana, Hajja and Mohammed (2015) who found that although the literacy rate was more among the boys than girls, was quite interesting to observe that girls were securing better grades than boys in almost all competitive examinations. Similarly, Mutchler, Uyar and Gungormus in Kulo (2021) supported the present findings in Table 2 with the view that female students perform better than male. They also maintained that both male and female students should be given equal opportunities in education and allowed to participate actively in teaching and learning situations. Be that as it may, using students centered learning strategy may positively influence students' academic achievement and help in eliminating gender inequality in courses in office technology and management generally and office management in particular. In agreement with the present findings in Table 2, Bayim (2016) opined that many boys in those days found school system overly hostile and they wrongly concluded that education and literacy were primarily female concerns. However, while boys may dominate the classroom in some places, the struggle for equal right and promotion of the girl child education has yielded positive fruits in most parts of the world with many girls in schools and many females holding higher management positions in work places.

On the other hand, the findings of this study shares the same position with Abakpa and Iji in Nwagwu (2022) who found that there was no significant difference in academic achievement of male and female students in learning. With their revelations, it is obvious that disparities in academic achievement of students might be disappearing creating equal competitive ground for both genders. Study carried out by Hyde and Mertz in Nwagwu (2022) revealed that both male and female students who were exposed to equal opportunity of deepening their understanding and access to assessing simple concept performed better than their female counterparts. Hyde and Mertz study revealed that female students had slight better performance than their male counterparts. This study has further shown that with careful and purposeful utilization of cooperative learning strategy, gender difference is not significant in the achievement of students in financial accounting. In the cause of this research, male and female students were shown to have demonstrated equal zeal and produced the same result in office management. This totally rules out the theory that gender places a particular group of students at advantage in the cause of learning financial accounting as a subject. Therefore, once the appropriate learning method is effectively applied, all students irrespective of gender are bound to excel.

Data analysis in Table 3 showed that the cooperative learning strategy is superior to the conventional method at the two levels of gender. For both male and female students the mean achievement scores are higher for the cooperative learning strategy. This implies that there is no interaction between method and gender on students mean achievement in Accounting. The null hypothesis as contain in Table 7 infers that there is no significant interaction between instructional methods and gender on students' mean achievement in accounting. The finding is in line with Okoli (2018) also buttressed the finding of this study as discovered that male and females taught using integrated method had adjusted means higher than their counterparts taught using individualized method. The study revealed that integrated learning methods were superior to individualize method for the two groups-males and female in facilitating students' achievement in advanced financial accounting. The finding of this study is also in line with Agu (2017) who found no interaction between methods of instructional delivery and gender on students' mean

achievement in business studies using peer-tutoring for both males and females. This finding is in consonance with that of Fabunmi (2018) who revealed that gender composition has a significant relationship with students' academic achievement and that gender composition has a significant influence on secondary school student's academic achievement. Diovu in Eya (2022) revealed that the interaction effects of treatment by gender on students' overall cognitive achievement in chemistry were not significant. This finding was contrary to the findings of Ureme (2023) who revealed that there was a difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught economics using project method in favour of females.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that cooperative learning strategy is more effective than the conventional (individualized learning) approach in facilitating students achievement in accounting. Male students performed better than their female counterparts when they learn accounting using the cooperative learning approach. There is no significant interaction between instructional methods and gender on students' mean achievement in accounting. Financial accounting as a subject should be taught using more cooperative learning strategy to help achieve the objectives of introducing financial accounting in senior secondary schools. The higher improvement in the mean interest scores in students exposed to cooperative learning strategy as found in the study could be as a result of some of its attributes and elements such as individual accountability, simultaneous interaction, cooperative skill and positive interdependent. Also, cooperative learning strategy enables equal participation which fosters interest and positive achievement among students

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1 School administrators should train and retrain financial accounting teachers on ways of adopting and effectively using cooperative learning strategy in learning;
- 2 Financial accounting teachers should encourage students to use cooperative learning strategy to enhance their academic achievement irrespective of their gender as teachers require students' cooperation for its effectiveness.
- 3 Government should organize seminars, workshops and conferences so that practicing teachers in the field would be opportune to learn how to make the best use cooperative learning strategy.

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